

1 **Supplementary data**

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3 **during a flowering season**

4 **Fig. S2. Distribution of the contig lengths of *Shorea curtisii* leaf transcriptome assembled**
5 **using Trinity**

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13 **differentially expressed unigenes in *Shorea curtisii* leaf transcriptome**

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15 **differentially expressed unigenes of *Shorea curtisii* leaf transcriptome**

16 **Tables S7A–D. Summary of GO annotations and enriched GO terms in the differentially**
17 **expressed unigenes of *Shorea curtisii* leaf transcriptome**

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1 **Fig. S1. The research strategy employed to study the leaf transcriptome of *Shorea***
 2 ***curtisii* during a flowering season**

3 (A) We extracted total RNA from 50–70 mg of leaf samples using conventional
 4 cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) buffer according to the method
 5 described by Kobayashi et al. (2013). The concentration of the extracted RNA was
 6 determined using NanoDrop ND2000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
 7 USA) and the integrity of the total RNA were measured using Bioanalyzer 2100
 8 (Agilent, USA). Prior to sequencing, cDNA library was prepared using the extracted
 9 RNA for each sample. (B) We utilized Trimmomatic v0.36 (Bolger et al., 2014) with
 10 default parameters to remove low quality bases and traces of Illumina adapters. *De*

1 *novo* assembly was performed using Trinity v2.8.5 (Grabherr et al., 2011) with
2 default parameters. We used TransDecoder v5.5.0 (<http://transdecoder.github.io>)
3 with default parameters to predict coding regions within each transcript and retain
4 only transcripts with complete open reading frame. The number of transcripts was
5 further reduced based on the predicted protein sequences by clustering highly similar
6 protein sequences using CD-HIT v4.8.1 (Fu et al., 2012) (parameters: -n 5 -c 1). The
7 quality of the assembly was assessed using BUSCO v5.2.1 (Simao et al., 2015). (C)
8 The unigenes were quantified using Salmon v1.5.1 (Patro et al., 2016) with default
9 parameters. (D) Differential expression analysis was performed using DESeq2
10 v1.32.0 (Love et al., 2014). The tool uses negative binomial distribution to model
11 raw counts data and relative log expression (RLE) for normalization. (E) The
12 transcripts were also searched against UniProt database (Consortium, 2020;
13 <https://ftp.uniprot.org/pub/databases/uniprot/>) using BLASTp v2.10 (Camacho et
14 al., 2009) with E-value cut-off: 1E-05, as well as Pfam v32.0 (El-Gebali et al., 2018;
15 <http://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/Pfam/>) and PANTHER v14.1 (Thomas et al.,
16 2003; <http://data.pantherdb.org/ftp/>) using InterProScan v5.36 (Jones et al., 2014).
17 The sequences were also assigned to GO terms (Ashburner et al., 2000) associated
18 with BLASTx matches against *A. thaliana* proteome obtained from Araport11
19 database (Cheng, C.-Y. et al., 2017; <https://www.arabidopsis.org/>). The unigenes
20 were searched against KEGG database (Kanehisa & Goto, 2000) using
21 BlastKOALA online tool (Kanehisa et al., 2016; <https://www.kegg.jp/blastkoala/>).
22 (F) Enrichment analyses were conducted to identify GO terms and KEGG pathways
23 enriched in differentially expressed unigenes using topGO package v2.40.0 (Alexa

1 & Rahnenfuhrer, 2020) ($P < 0.05$) and KOBAS v3.0 (Bu et al., 2021) ($FDR < 0.05$),
2 respectively. We used WEGO (Ye et al., 2006; <https://wego.genomics.cn/>) to plot
3 the output of the GO terms.

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1 **Fig. S2. Distribution of the contig lengths of *Shorea curtisii* leaf transcriptome**
2 **assembled using Trinity**

1 **Fig. S3. Classification of *Shorea curtisii* unigenes into three main GO categories (cellular**
 2 **component, molecular function, and biological process)**

3 Out of 36,156 unigenes that could be assigned to GO terms, 35,146 (97.2%) were
 4 classified into ‘cellular component’ (CC) category, 28,182 (77.9%) were classified into
 5 ‘molecular function’ (MF) category, and 27,115 (74.9%) were classified into ‘biological
 6 process’ (BP) category. The GO annotation was summarized at level 2 with a total of
 7 47 GO terms across the three GO categories. ‘Cellular process’ and ‘metabolic process’
 8 terms are dominant (54.3% and 50.2% out of total GO annotated unigenes, respectively)
 9 in BP, while ‘binding’ (48.6%) and ‘catalytic activity’ (41.6%) showed the highest
 10 percentages in MF. Both ‘cell’ (84.9%) and ‘cell part’ (84.9%) were the dominant terms
 11 in CC (Table S5A).

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Table S1. Details of meteorological data and sampling time

Time point	Date	Developmental stage	Daily temperature ^a (°C)			Daily rainfall (mm)	Sampling time ^b	
			Min	Max	Mean		C1	C2
TP-A	18 December 2013	Vegetative	22.7	34.8	28.0	3.7	11:10	12:10
TP-B	02 April 2014	Inflorescence	24.0	33.9	27.2	0.4	11:10	12:30
TP-C	17 June 2014	Fruiting/abortion	22.5	34.5	28.2	0.0	11:15	12:20

^a Daily temperature record which consists of minimum temperature (Min), maximum temperature (Max), and mean temperature (Mean).

^b Sampling time in 24-h format for individual trees, C1 and C2.

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Table S2. Summary of BUSCO analysis

Description	No. of genes recovered	Percentage (Over total BUSCO genes)
Complete BUSCO ^a (C)	1,397	86.6
Complete and single-copy BUSCO (S)	499	30.9
Complete and duplicated BUSCO (D)	898	55.6
Uni Fragmented BUSCO (F)	54	3.3
Missing BUSCO (M)	163	10.1
Total BUSCO genes ^b	1,614	100.0

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^a Complete BUSCO genes (C) = S + D

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^b Total BUSCO genes = C + F + M

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